

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7798046

“OXYGEN CONCLAVE”

a WEBINAR

ORG SECRETARY DR JANARDAN BHATT

15th ACADEMIC MEET 2020

31th OCTOBER 2020

MULTI DISCIPLINARY CONFERENCE /CME ON:
WEBINAR

ON

OXYGEN CONCLAVE

JOURNEY OXYGEN IN HUMAN BODY

BASIC TO APPLIED

We invite all faculties, residents and post graduate medical students of medical colleges to participate in 15th Academic meet a CME/ conference on “JOURNEY OXYGEN IN HUMAN BODY BASIC TO APPLIED “
OXYGEN CONCLAVE

We have invited experts to talk and participate in said subjects. Abstract of your paper, poster, speech are invited with Registration Contact Emails:

forum99in@gmail.com Online

Registration link

<https://forms.gle/KQqtB9CR4pvE2RdQ8>

Down load form

Conference is accredited by Gujarat Medical Council [Applied]

We have also kept a competition of online poster and oral presentation of research paper for Post graduate students, residents and faculties also .

RULES:

1] For poster presentation

Size: 3’x4’

Orientation: portrait submitted 10 days before the conference

Abstract: As oral presentation 2] ORAL PRESENTATION:

Time limit:

Maximum 5 minutes

Soft copy of presentation in the form of power point presentation to bring on day of conference

ABSTRACT: must be submitted on or before Deadline: 15th August 2019

ABSTRACT OF PAPER/POSTER

Maximum 200 words must include:

- 1] Name of topic
- 2] Name of presenter
- 3] Department
- 4] Affiliation with college/Hospital
- 5] Name of PG teacher
- 6] Key words
- 7] Introduction
- 8] Methods
- 9] Results
- 10] Name of statistical test
- 11] conclusions.
- 12] References

Speakers can send abstract of their presentation and will be published in Souvenir /Abstract book

REGISTRATION FORM:
FOR FORUM

Name: (Dr.Mr./Mrs./Miss)

GMC/IMC: Registration Number:

Mobile No :

Email ID:

Age

Sex:

Hospital/college:

Department:

Presentation : choose
one

ORAL or POSTER:

Title of Presentation:

Here with I certify that Dr

_____ is our resident /pg
student.

I assure that he/she will attend the conference from 9 AM to 5 pm without failure. I will permit him/her to attend the conference/CME Program and keep away from any emergency duty on conference day. I take full responsibility of his attendance in conference & failure to attend he/ she will not entitled to get certificate refund of registration fee.

Signature of PG teacher or HOD